

NDAC/LO/070
1986, April 2

Influence of decreased slit-width on the HIPPARCOS binaries
by S. Söderhjelm

In NDAC/LO/067, increased slit-width (decreased modulation coefficients) was found to give a decreased astrometric accuracy for most binaries. The mean result was an 8% lower accuracy for a 9% increase of the slit-width. A similar study has now been made with decreased slit-width.

The changes from the nominal OTF-values are -13 % in I_0 , +2.5 % in M_1 , and +18.5 % in M_2 , corresponding to -9.3 % in the slit-width (E. Zeis, telefax 1986 Febr² 11). Also, the third harmonic M_3 is now significantly larger, 0.021 versus 0.006 for $B-V = 0.5$. As before, the modified and the standard simulation/solution programs were run with otherwise identical input, and about 70 different binaries were generated. Each binary gives four different astrometric results, for primary and secondary components and for "free" and "fixed" solutions. For lack of contrary evidence, all separations (0.3 - 34 arcsec) were treated equally, and simple mean rms-ratios ("narrow"/nominal astrometric error) were computed.

For the equal-magnitude pairs (standard Ser.C of NDAC/LO/066), the astrometric rms-values are decreased to 0.97 ± 0.02 relative to the nominal. For pairs with $\Delta m = 1.5^m$ (Ser. B), the mean ratio is instead 1.04 ± 0.02 . In both cases, an individual rms-ratio has a standard deviation close to 0.20, and a much larger number of tests would be required to see if this difference is really significant. For the moment, the conclusion is that a small decrease of the slit-width has rather little effect, but possibly, that effect may be negative. (The "non-linearity" as compared with the wide-slit results is probably due to the increased M_3).